

DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation: *This article provides a brief overview of how to develop young students' speaking skills, what grammar rules to use, and how to improve their English speaking skills.*

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Human speech develops gradually, the process of speech development consists of several stages. In the first year of a child's life, anatomical, physiological, and psychological conditions are created to master speech. This stage of speech development is preparation, pre-speech. In the second year of life, the child practically masters human speech. But this speech is grammatical in nature - even though the child is already building sentences, it has no declensions, conjugations, prelogs, and conjunctions. Grammatically correct oral speech is formed in the third year of a child's life, but at this stage the child makes many mistakes in both morphology and word formation. Further development of speech occurs in middle and high school age, and by the age of seven, by the time a child enters school, he or she has mastered his or her native language system sufficiently and is fluent in spoken language. Going to school can make a big difference in a child's speech development. These shifts are related to the fact that a child's speech is subject to new requirements related to the learning of many new learning disciplines. For children under the age of 1, school-age speech is a practical means of communication with other people, and in the process of its formation, then in school-age children, speech is also a means of mastering the cognitive system.

Without learning the language itself, without mastering literacy - reading and writing, it is clear that a child's speech cannot function as a systematic and comprehensive knowledge of reality. Therefore, in a learning setting, the child's spoken language becomes his or her specific learning topic. The student learns three aspects of language: phonetic, lexical, and grammatical. In the process of language learning, all types of student speech are improved and developed. Written language development. Especially when written speech is more valuable in developing a student's speech. A person who is fluent in written language has a much wider range of

communication possibilities. A student who has mastered the written language can express and convey his / her opinion in writing to a person who does not have it. Using the same written language, he can learn other people's opinions and, most importantly, gain knowledge by reading textbooks and other books. A student's written speech is subject to much greater demands than his or her oral speech. The written presentation of this or that study material should be strictly consistent and coherent, understandable to the reader. The student's written and oral speech develop in unity and interact with each other. Mastering written speech involves reading and writing skills, knowledge of grammar and spelling rules. The development of written speech begins with mastering the reading process. According to the research of T. G. Egorov, the acquisition of reading skills goes through three main stages. In the first stage - analytically - the reader gets acquainted with the names of the letters and how these letters are combined into syllables, from syllables to words, using the corresponding speech sounds.

At this stage, the synthesis of letters into syllables and syllables into words is slow and with certain difficulties. This is explained by the following psychological reasons: first, because the student has not yet been able to distinguish the graphic style of the letters well, their recognition is sluggish and erroneous; second, the reader has difficulty connecting letters to matching sounds and often makes mistakes. As a result, there is a delay in the synthesis of word elements and the evil of recognizing it. In the second stage - synthetic - the student synthesizes the elements of the word without much difficulty and faster. However, even at this stage, there are errors in word synthesis. They are the result of schoolchildren rushing to read before distinguishing the elements that make up a word, i.e. by guessing. Often, these errors occur when a word that is read outwardly sounds like another familiar word. In the third stage - analytical-synthetic - the reading process in schoolchildren is based on the rapid differentiation and integration of word elements. This is a fluent and accurate reading phase. The speed of reading from class to class increases significantly. For example, a first-grader who completes a primer study reads aloud about three times slower than a fourth-grader, which in turn reads twice as slowly as a tenth-grader. Meaningful, "thinking" reading relies on the development of complex thinking processes that enable the reader to understand the basic and important ideas of the text's content. Meaningful reading is not given immediately, but develops gradually, in the process of education and upbringing. The teacher needs to know both the reasons that hinder the development of reading and the means that accelerate its development. Experience in school and psychological research show that young students' misunderstanding of a particular text is linked to children's poor vocabulary, inability to find the main idea when they read, and to separate parts of the text. It depends on whether or not. putting the work into a general context, and so on. Overcoming these

shortcomings in the development of meaningful reading requires special effort from the teacher. First of all, it is necessary to develop and enrich children's vocabulary. And for this, it is important to know what vocabulary the child has and how accurately these words express the content of the concepts. School children should be taught to find the main idea of a story or a passage from a textbook text. important words and statements in which this idea is expressed. To do this, children are taught to plan the story they are reading, to look for the most appropriate headings for stories, paragraphs, parts of a plan, etc. The text is read expressively by the teacher and then by the students themselves; helps to understand the content of the text being read. Expressive reading reveals the semantic content of a text using vivid intonation and logical emphasis. To develop your English speaking skills, we must first pay attention to pronunciation. If we do not pronounce English words correctly, our speech may become unintelligible to others. We will need to examine and study the correct pronunciation of all the English words and phrases in our vocabulary one by one. You don't have to master English phonetics to learn the correct pronunciation of words. It may be sufficient to study the transcription of words in dictionaries to know how individual words are pronounced.

REFERENCES

1. Qodirova. F. R. Kadyrova R. M. Theory and methods of development of children's speech. -T. : Istiqlol. 2006.
2. Qodirova. F. R. Kadyrova R. M. Methods of teaching a second language to preschool children. -T. : Sano-Standart. 2004.
3. Babayeva DR Theory and methods of speech development. -TDPU. : 2018.